

**MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HIGH SPEED STEEL BASE
COMPOSITES CONTAINING TiC AND TiN CERAMIC ADDITIONS**

M.M.Oliveira (1), J.D.Bolton (2)

(1) Dept. Materials Technology, INETI, Lisbon, Portugal

(2) Dept. Mechanical Engineering, Univ. Bradford, UK

ABSTRACT

In order to improve wear resistance, TiC and TiN particles were incorporated into a AISI M3/2 high speed steel, liquid phase sintered in the temperature range 1140-1170°C. The addition of the ceramic particles did not affect significantly the overall hardness of the composites. Results of bend strength tests indicated that fracture strength was determined both by the particle size of the ceramic additions, since they act as crack initiators, and by the toughness of the high speed steel matrix. Fracture toughness varied from one composite to another, due to the reactions going on between the TiC and TiN particles and the surrounding phases during the sintering process.

Keywords: Composites, Steel Matrix, Sintering, Mechanical Properties, Titanium Carbide, Titanium Nitride.

1. INTRODUCTION

The materials studied in this work were metal-matrix composites based on the high speed steel AISI M3/2, with copper phosphide and graphite additions, in order to lower the sintering temperature to values in the range 1120-1150°C, by promoting a liquid phase sintering process [1-3]. The aim was to develop an economically competitive processing route, which might be carried out in the industrial continuous furnaces, in order to produce wear resistant composites for use as engineering components, by incorporating hard ceramic particles in the base material, at the powder compaction stage. As for the ceramic particles, attention was focused on reactive ceramics such as titanium carbide (TiC) and titanium nitride (TiN), on the basis of earlier experimental results [4-7], which showed that both sintering behaviour and fracture strength of the composite materials were significantly affected by the reactivity of the ceramic particles with the matrix: such reactivity was apparent from the formation of an interfacial layer

of vanadium rich MC type carbides or carbonitrides at the TiC/matrix and TiN/matrix interfaces, respectively.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The base material was prepared by dry blending the AISI M3/2 steel powder (chemical composition: bal.Fe-1.1C-3.8Cr-5.0W-6.3Mo-2.7V, wt%; mean particle size:50 μ m) with 7wt% Cu₃P and 0.5wt% graphite for 15 min in a Turbula mixer; the additions (10 vol%) of the ceramic powders were made to the base material by blending for another 15 min. The ceramic additions were from the same batches used in previous research work [4-7]. Their nominal particle sizes were experimentally confirmed by a sedimentation technique. Three batches (6 μ m; 16 μ m and 42 μ m) of TiC and two batches (7 μ m and 12 μ m) of TiN were used.

The mixtures were compacted uniaxially compacted at pressures in the range 600-800 MPa as specimens for sintering tests with the approximate dimensions 26x6x4mm. The specimens were vacuum sintered at 1 Pa in the temperature range of 1080-1210°C, holding for 30 min at temperature, in order to determine the sintering curves. A slow heating rate of 10°C/min was used, with 5 min holds at 890, 930 and 1000°C, to allow outgassing of the specimens. After sintering, the specimens were furnace cooled to room temperature. Densities were determined by the Archimedes method, the specimens being previously coated with lacquer, in order to seal the surface against water penetration.

The following mechanical properties were determined: Vickers hardness, fracture strength and fracture toughness. Fracture strength was determined by three point bend tests, using specimens with the final dimensions of 20x4x2mm; the specimens were longitudinally ground with diamond wheels on all surfaces and the tensile faces were metallographically polished to 3 μ m diamond finish. The transverse rupture strength (TRS) was calculated after the ASTM standard B528-76, using the following relationship:

$$TRS = 3Pl / (2bh^2)$$

where P=load, l=span, b= specimen width, h=specimen depth. The span used was 16 mm and the cross head speed 0.1 mm/min.

Fracture toughness was also determined by a three point bend testing method, using dimensions which complied with the standard BS 5447, and was calculated from the following relationship:

$$K_{1C} = 3PLY / (BW^{1.5})$$

where P is the load and B(breadth)=3mm, W(width)=6mm, 2L(span)=24mm, while Y is given by

$$Y = 1.93 (a/W)^{0.5} - 3.07 (a/W)^{1.5} + 14.53 (a/W)^{2.5} - 25.11 (a/W)^{3.5} + 25.80 (a/W)^{4.5}$$

The test specimens were pre-cracked to give a monotonically sharp crack of length=a and a a/W ratio between 0.35 and 0.6. Pre cracking was achieved by the arrest of an impact induced crack through the application of a transverse compressive force applied just below a chevron shaped notch cut by a diamond slitting saw into the test piece. The impact energy was applied by a weight falling onto a

cemented carbide wedge placed vertically into the chevron notch. The pre-cracked test pieces were immersed in a nital etching solution before testing to stain the pre-crack fracture surface, thus allowing clear identification of the pre-crack, compared with the final fracture surface after testing, which permitted measurement of the original crack length (a) to be made by a travelling microscope.

Characterisation of the microstructures produced in the various composites and the identification of phases was performed by both optical and scanning electron microscopy, including the use of a quantitative image analysis programme, and also by X-Ray diffraction.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Sintering behaviour and microstructures

The sintering curves (Fig.1) of the base material (M3/2+7wt%Cu₃P+0.5wt%C) and of the composites containing 10vol% TiC or TiN ceramic additions showed that full densities were obtained in all the composite mixtures. Maximum density was obtained at 1120°C for the base material; at 1140°C in the case of the composite material with the coarser (42µm) TiC particles; and at 1170°C for the remaining ceramic additions. The effect of the compacting pressure of the powder on the as sintered density was found to be not significant in the range 600-800 MPa, and therefore the larger specimens for fracture toughness testing were compacted at 600 MPa, while the specimens for the bend tests had been compacted at 800 MPa.

Typical microstructures for the different composites in the as-sintered condition are shown in Fig. 2. After sintering at 1140°C, the base material (Fig 2a) showed angular M₆C and round MC carbides in a matrix which was predominantly martensitic (due to the cooling rate in the sintering furnace); residual copper was dispersed as isolated pools and pearlite areas were visible in prior austenite grains, while other austenite grains showed a precipitation of fine carbides; the eutectic areas which were observed in association with M₆C and MC carbides, and also as some grain boundary films, were found (by EDS microanalysis) to be iron rich phosphide, containing also molybdenum, chromium, vanadium and copper; when the sintering temperature was increased to 1170°C, these eutectic areas and films coarsened significantly (Fig. 2b). The presence of retained austenite was detected by X-Ray diffraction analysis.

The addition of the ceramic particles had some effects on the microstructure of the base material. Higher sintering temperatures were required to obtain full density, since pores tended to remain between ceramic particles (when agglomerated) and sometimes also at the ceramic/matrix interfaces. The ceramic particles tested in this work were reactive ceramics with a clearly detectable interaction with the matrix: in the cases of both TiC (Fig. 2c) and TiN (Fig.2d) particles, an interfacial layer was formed at the ceramic/matrix interfaces by a precipitation of vanadium-rich MC type carbides (or carbonitrides in the case of the TiN particles). Whenever the ceramic particles showed cracks (formed during either the compaction of the powders or the sintering process), these cracks were observed to be completely filled by an iron-phosphorus and vanadium rich MC carbide phase, which indicated that a liquid phase must have surrounded the particles and

Figure 1. Sintering curves of the base material and TiC and TiN composites.

Figure 2. Microstructures of the base material and TiC and TiN composites: base material, as sintered at 1140 (a) and 1170°C(b); composite with 10 vol% TiC (6 μ m) as sintered at 1170°C (c) ; and composite with 10 vol% TiN (12 μ m) as sintered at 1170°C (d).

penetrated into the cracks during the sintering stage. Regarding the matrix, martensite was still the main constituent, followed by pearlite ; areas with a fine precipitation of carbides were also observed, and X-Ray diffraction showed that the amount of retained austenite was increased by the addition of either TiC or TiN particles.

3.2.Mechanical properties.

The results of bend strength and fracture toughness tests (which represents the average of at least five tests in each type of composite material), as well as hardness determinations, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.Effect of ceramic additions and sintering temperature on fracture strength, fracture toughness and hardness of the composite materials

Material	Sint.Temp.	TRS(MNm ⁻²)	K _{1c} (MNm ^{-3/2})	HV30
Base	1140°C	1362±67	17.05±0.85	750± 9
	1170°C	1244±51	15.96±1.43	739±17
TiC 6µm	1170°C	1530±95	16.10±0.83	752±19
TiC 16µm	1170°C	1148±74	18.24±0.90	777±11
TiC 42µm	1140°C	1290±88	17.15±0.78	771± 8
	1170°C	1194±50	17.59±0.96	801±17
TiN 7µm	1170°C	1319±71	14.73±0.87	677±25
TiN 12µm	1170°C	1140±50	14.85±1.08	748±12

The overall hardness of the different composites did not reflect the presence of the ceramic particles, which may be due to two reasons:(i) due to their rather small volume fractions, the hard ceramic additions were well dispersed and isolated in the matrix, without forming a rigid skeleton of interconnected particles; (ii) higher retained austenite contents in the matrix of the composite materials were also responsible for reducing their hardness.

Regarding bend strength, there were two effects to be noticed:the effect of sintering temperature and the one of the presence of the ceramic particles.In spite of reducing porosity, increasing the sintering temperature yielded oversintered microstructures with coarser eutectic areas and grain boundary phosphide films (Figs 2a and 2b), and therefore bend strength decreased in the materials sintered at 1170°C, this variation being more significant in the case of the base material.

The addition of the ceramic particles, hard and brittle (as shown by their tendency to crack during the compaction stage), was expected to lower bend strength, since the ceramic additions were likely to act as crack initiators, according to their size and shape:taking into account the values of ceramic particle sizes, the bend strengths of the two TiN composites seemed clearly related with the dimensions of the ceramic particles, being significantly higher

for the composite with the finer addition. In the case of the TiC composites, the finer (6 μ m) TiC addition yielded the higher bend strength (even higher than the one of the base material), which might be attributed to further reduction of the volume fraction and particle dimensions of the ceramic addition during the sintering process, as a consequence of its higher reactivity, which yielded more TiC dissolution, as indicated by preliminary results of quantitative metallographic analysis. In order to understand the factors which controlled bend strength of these materials, fracture toughness determinations were therefore necessary.

The values of fracture toughness showed that increasing the sintering temperature from 1140 to 1170°C caused a decrease of the fracture toughness of the base material, in a similar manner as already described for bend strength. This effect of sintering temperature became not significant in the case of the composite with TiC addition. Comparing the composite materials with the base material sintered at the same temperature (1170°C), it was concluded that the fracture toughness of the base material was increased by the addition of TiC and decreased by the addition of TiN. Comparison between the individual values showed that very little difference existed between the fracture toughness of the same type of composites with different ceramic particle size, which indicated that toughness was mainly dependent from the high speed steel matrix. Regarding the TiC composites, the higher toughness may be explained by the higher levels of retained austenite, as compared with the ones of the base material. However, increased retained austenite contents were also found for the TiN composites, which fracture toughness was lower than the one of the base material.

The values of the fracture toughness of both the base material and the TiC composites agree quite well with results already reported on the same type of materials [6]. The fact that the present K_{Ic} values were significantly lower than those published for vacuum sintered conventional high speed steels (20-30 MNm^{-3/2}, [9]) was attributed to the presence of the phosphorus which was added to promote the liquid phase sintering.

The lower bend strengths of the composites as compared with the one of the base material might be explained by crack initiation in the ceramic particles, followed by propagation through the steel matrix. Therefore, bend strength would be controlled first by the size of the initial crack, which was related to the particle size of the ceramic additions after sintering, and then by the toughness of the high speed steel matrix, which varied from one composite to another, due to the reactions going on between the ceramic particles and the surrounding phases during the sintering process. Different amounts of pearlite and retained austenite were formed by these reactions.

Further work is therefore required, namely through microhardness determinations, metallographic observations of fractured specimens and bend tests associated with metallography of the tensile faces of the specimens under load, in order to obtain a fuller understanding of the mechanisms of initiation, growth and propagation of cracks in these materials.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1- High speed steel metal matrix composites containing 10 vol% of TiC and TiN ceramic additions with different particle sizes were

vacuum sintered to full density at 1140 and 1170°C, using a liquid phase sintering process, by adding a copper phosphorus alloy.

2- The addition of the ceramic particles did not significantly effect the overall hardness of the composites.

3- Fracture toughness of the base material was found to be increased by the addition of the TiC particles, which was attributed to the increased retained austenite content in the high speed steel matrix. The composites containing TiN particles yielded however lower values of fracture toughness than the ones of the base material. Fracture toughness varied from one composite to another due to the reactions going on between the ceramic additions and the surrounding phases during the sintering process, yielding different amounts of martensite, pearlite and retained austenite upon cooling.

4- The effect of the ceramic additions on the fracture strength of the composite materials was affected both by the size of the ceramic particles, which acted as crack initiators, and by the toughness of the high speed steel matrix.

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